

Research Article

Bearbud Application

Ayu Kamareenna Abdullah Thani ^{1,*}, Nurul Nadhira Amalin Azhari ², Nur Ezaty Amira Ali ³, Nur Izzah Inani Mohamad Nasir ⁴, Nur Nabilah Kassim ⁵, and Nur Farisha Husna Ahmad Sukri ⁶

¹ Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; ayukamareenna@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0001-7851-2354

² Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; nurulnadhira@uitm.edu.my; 0009-0008-7848-0426

³ Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; 2021627708@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0002-2753-8911

⁴ Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; 2021816276@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0001-9355-9115

⁵ Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; 2021843616@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0007-1593-8746

⁶ Universiti Teknologi MARA Cawangan Kelantan; 2021609272@student.uitm.edu.my; 0009-0009-8259-2794

* nurulnadhira@uitm.edu.my; 011-33718616.

Abstract: Executing mental health online consultations entails giving people the chance to participate in therapy sessions with licensed physicians or mental health specialists via digital platforms. To commence a consultation, users of the BearBud application can opt for the "Consultation" feature, choose their preferred physician from a roster of available specialists, and start a chat session. Users are free to discuss any mental health issues they may have, ask any questions they may have, and get direction and advice from the physician during the consultation. It is significant to remember that the BearBud app only covers ten therapy sessions; users who would like to continue consultations beyond this time frame may have to pay through the app. This method enables people to handle their mental health issues in a practical and approachable way, obtain professional guidance, and obtain remote mental health support.

Keywords: Mental health¹, online consultations², professional guidance³, remote mental health support⁴

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13888324

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

The issue that has been identified to carry out this innovation is that there are too many cases of mental problems in society today as a result of the millennial age, which now requires strong mental health to continue life. This is because nowadays most of the environment is filled with people who behave toxic and negative. It puts pressure on people who have thin mental powers. This is said because people who cannot stand such an environment will experience emotional stress, which will lead them to do unwanted things. For example, hurting themselves, locking themselves in a room alone, and deciding to end their history by committing suicide. According to Wang et al. (2020), stress at work and project success have been demonstrated to be negatively correlated with toxic work environments. In addition, there is the issue of societal misconceptions against the mentally ill.

Things like this emotional stress cannot be seen physically, like an accident that we can see with our eyes. However, the pressure of this feeling can only be experienced by those who experience it. Among the mental illnesses available are depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, insomnia, schizophrenia, and many more. Therefore, other communities see this matter as trivial and unimportant to them. According to Corrigan and Watson (2020), states that they referring to the mentally ill are

challenged by stereotypes and prejudices stemming from misconceptions about mental illness. The next issue is how people with mental health problems access mental health services. This is because the community that faces this disease has its way of treating it. Most of the people who face this problem do not know where to get treatment to treat their illness, especially those who live in rural areas. Indirectly, they also do not get information about their disease. So, when the patient himself does not know how to access mental health services, he cannot treat their illness properly, which will put more pressure on them. According to Munira et al. (2023), this study identified a number of obstacles to receiving mental health treatments, including financial constraints, travel expenses, stigma, a lack of assistance, and high treatment costs. These obstacles lead to difficulties in receiving treatment and make it harder to receive mental health services.

There are several opportunities to address mental health issues, among which is increasing public awareness and education to reduce the stigma that can hurt the mentally ill. The outside community that lacks knowledge about this mental problem will be given a broad approach to this matter. They need to be made aware that mental care is very important to avoid unwanted things such as suicide and self-harm. According to Siddique et al. (2022), growing knowledge about mental illness promotes greater understanding and compassion for people who struggle with mental health issues. Mental illnesses that stigmatize people or make it more difficult to provide mental health care might result from ignorance regarding psychiatric illnesses. Additionally, these innovations can expand access to affordable mental health services.

People who experience early mental stages can also use it to overcome this problem at an early stage. This is good because dealing with it at an early stage can reduce the critical risk to the patient. This is because they can prevent their illness from getting worse in the future. Furthermore, mental patients who only experience early symptoms are easier to treat than patients who have been suffering from this disease for a long time. Indirectly, it makes it easier for doctors to treat their patients. According to Raaj et al. (2021), significant revisions to Malaysian mental health legislation have occurred, with a service-level shift from custodial care to community care and the establishment of a research and organizational development foundation to enhance mental health service delivery. In turn, this can help create a more supportive environment. This is because mental patients can express what they have been hiding all this time. This will lighten the burden. This thing seems to give a new spirit to the mentally ill, who have been harbouring feelings of loneliness for a long time. In other words, mental patients need people to listen to their expressions because they are not able to store all their feelings at this time. According to Ekaputri (2023), social support groups and community involvement could create an environment of encouragement that could mitigate mental illness. For example, students need someone to listen to their problems about studying so that it doesn't put more pressure on them. But other people don't take this matter seriously because they think that learning is easy and they don't need to feel stressed to learn.

2. SOFTWARE DESIGN

"BearBud" application design:

1. Tailored Advice and Personalized Treatment: The app provides personalized mental health advice, treatment plans, and in-depth discussions tailored to individual concerns, extending beyond general features the free version of the app.
2. Remote Therapy and Counselling: BearBud is an online therapy platform that connects users with mental health professionals. It provides accessibility to professional help from the comfort of your own environment, especially for those who have difficulty accessing in-person services.

3. Licensing Mental Health Tools: The app licenses its mental health resources to healthcare providers, telemedicine platforms, or corporate wellness programs, expanding its reach and impact for a broader audience.

4. Support for Mental Health Awareness: BearBud collaborates with NGOs and the government to offer mental health awareness programs, providing educational resources and community involvement opportunities. This initiative contributes to raising awareness and reducing stigma surrounding mental health issues.

5. User-Friendly Interface and Accessibility: The app provides online mental health consultation, connecting patients with professionals and offering support to registered patients, even when they're away from their usual area.

3. PROCESS EXECUTION

The process involved in using the BearBud application:

1. Registration/Login Interface: To access the BearBud application's features, users must first register or log in. This requires them to enter their username, email address, and password. The registration/login interface is critical for any app because it is the first component of rapid prototyping.

2. Self-Care Services: The app provides self-care resources to assist users in managing their mental health, including journaling, mood analysis, diary writing, and meditation techniques. Activities that support self-care and emotional regulation are made possible for users through this process.

3. Consultation Services: For mental health consultations, users can start chat sessions with licensed physicians. Users can extend consultations beyond the allotted ten therapy sessions by remitting payment via the app. Through this process, users can get professional advice and support for mental health issues.

4. Programs and Services: Users can participate in a variety of mental health awareness programs, such as Game Changers, Podcast, Virtually Fit, and Forum Video. These programs are designed to help people who are struggling with mental health concerns by offering them support and direction, which in turn helps them manage their mental illness.

4. FUTURE WORK

The effectiveness of the BearBud application needs to be monitored from time to time or get feedback from users so that it can improve based on user preferences and the latest progress. As for example, the design and functionality of the PTSD coach app have undergone multiple significant revisions in response to user and healthcare provider stakeholder feedback. Despite their infrequent app visits, the majority of users interacted with the main content. Researchers were able to determine what aspects of the program users found appealing and what should be improved by analyzing which features were used more often than others. Future research should aim to more flexibly examine the utility of different app features as well as to investigate questions on understanding effectiveness to better match the intervention format to the person and optimizing engagement to enhance the likelihood of a meaningful impact with the app. For BearBud designers, updating the application in the future may be by adding some features that are more focused on the user's condition such as track progress which users had the option to view a graph and specifics of their previous self-assessments, set a reminder to do future self-assessments, and perform a self-assessment of their symptoms and receive comments. Meanwhile, another feature is safety plan for suicide prevention which users were initially provided information on the goal of the safety plan, encouraged to talk with a provider about

it, and given resources for dealing with emergencies and choices for obtaining medical attention. The six sequential phases that made up the safety plan consisted of a pre-planned, customized set of techniques meant to assist people in controlling mental health emergencies (such as suicide thoughts) rather than acting impulsively. These steps correlate to identifying (1) warning indicators, (2) self-coping mechanisms, (3) social contacts and places for purposes of distraction, (4) family and friends for purposes of crisis management, (5) mental health specialists and agencies, and (6) ways to prevent access to fatal means. Steps 3 through 6 entails adding a contact, and steps 3 and 6 consist of two separate parts. If a user completed all six stages with complete information, the safety plan was considered complete for analysis. As shown in the figure is the PTSD coach apps that may be one of our references for future improvements.

Figure 1: PTSD COACH APPS

5. CONCLUSION

An alarming rise in mental illness has been linked to a number of variables that lead people to make poor decisions that end up resulting in self-harm or other severe consequences. Therefore, addressing mental health problems is important for a variety of reasons that significantly impact an individual's overall well-being and quality of life. This is because mental health directly affects a person's ability to function in various aspects of life. On the other hand, dealing with mental health problems ensures that individuals can live a satisfying and productive life. For example, if an individual is dealing with a lot of stresses and obstacles during this point, it can lead to a range of physical, social, and emotional problems. Thus, mental health providers need to employ communication channels to educate the local community about the causes of mental diseases. Accompanying the recent surge in interest and understanding of mental health has been a greater need for improving mental quality of life. This led to the emergence of the idea of mental health services and a rise in the need to use information and communication technology (ICT) to manage mental health, including social network services (SNS) and mobile communication. Modern approaches to managing

mental health include the therapeutic usage of applications linked to mental health and mobile app-based intervention programmers. As a result, the designer's concept led to the development of the mental health app BearBud. People can manage their own health care, get advice from licensed medical professionals, and take advantage of mental health programs by using this application. Users can update their current moods which will be monitored by an available doctor. In the journal area, users can also update their daily tasks or to-do list. Furthermore, another self-care tool is mediation, which allows users to reduce stress by listening to zikr, music, or storytelling while overcoming mental health issues. The user's recommended doctors will be mentioned in the consultation area. Individuals are required to begin paying for therapy sessions after the first ten free consultations. If they are interested in taking part in a mental health program, they can look over the schedule of events and choose a time, day, and location that works for them. By doing this, the designer intends to lessen the mental health issues that individuals may face.

References

- Corrigan, P. W., & Watson, A. C. (2020). Understanding the impact of stigma on people with mental illness. *World Psychiatry: Official Journal of the World Psychiatric Association (WPA)*, 1(1), 16–20. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1489832/>.
- Ekaputri, N. T. (2023). Supportive Environment as Mental Health Intervention on Psychological Well-Being from Foreign Language Learning Activity. *Jurnal Promkes*, 11(1), 117–126. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jpk.v11.i1.2023.117-126>.
- Munira, L., Liamputtong, P., & Viwattanakulvanid, P. (2023). Barriers and facilitators to access mental health services among people with mental disorders in Indonesia: A qualitative study. *Belitung Nursing Journal*, 9(2), 110–117. <https://doi.org/10.33546/bnj.2521>.
- Raaj, S., Navanathan, S., Tharmaselan, M., & Lally, J. (2021). Mental disorders in Malaysia: an increase in lifetime prevalence. *BJPsych International*, 18(4), 97–99. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bji.2021.4>.
- Siddique, Md. A. B., Ovi, M. R., Ahammed, T., Chowdhury, M. A. B., & Uddin, M. J. (2022). Mental health knowledge and awareness among university students in Bangladesh. *Heliyon*, 8(10), e11084. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11084>.
- Wang, Z., Zaman, S., Rasool, S. F., Zaman, Q. uz, & Amin, A. (2020). Exploring the Relationships Between a Toxic Workplace Environment, Workplace Stress, and Project Success with the Moderating Effect of Organizational Support: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan. *Risk Management and Healthcare Policy*, 13(1), 1055–1067. <https://doi.org/10.2147/RMHP.S256155>.